

Deliverable 4.2

Implementation procedure and work programme for the joint researcher mobility and Young Leaders Academy programmes

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1. Introduction

As part of the EUTOPIA 2050¹ and the EUTOPIA TRAIN projects, the EUTOPIA Alliance is committed to developing new initiatives aimed at promoting career perspectives, scientific exchange and research impact for the EUTOPIA research community with a special focus on early-to-mid career researchers.

The EUTOPIA 2050 project already developed researcher mobility pilot programmes to support EUTOPIA collaborations such as the Young Leader Academy (YLA), the Researcher Mobility, and the Doctoral Mobility programmes.

The Workpackage 4 of the EUTOPIA-TRAIN project (WP4) “Sharing best practices for, and developing strategies to, strengthen human capital” elaborates on these pilot programmes, while addressing H2020 R&I transformation module « developing and implementing strategies for strengthening human capital in research and innovation and for enabling balanced brain circulation”. More specifically, WP4 aims at developing a Human Resource strategy to support the emergence of a challenge-driven knowledge-creation community across the EUTOPIA Alliance. This work

The three main objectives of the WP4 are:

1. to support the integration of the R&I communities of the alliance through adequate tools and instruments and dedicated pilot programs.
2. to support the promotion of talent through a shared approach to skill upgrading and career development and common training programs.
3. to develop a common long-term EUTOPIA Human Resource strategy

This report is related to the following tasks and sub-tasks:

- WP4.1 Developing mutualized support for R&I collaboration and training - Task 4.1.2 Supporting research collaboration (Researcher mobility programme)
- WP4.2 Promoting specific training and mobility programmes in early stages of research careers - Task 4.2.1 Expansion of the Young Leader academy.

These tasks concern the research mobility tools that EUTOPIA Alliance intends to use to better integrate the EUTOPIA research communities, connect EUTOPIA research to the local and regional contexts and finally to the societal challenges shared by the Alliance.

¹ The EUTOPIA 2050 project has received funding from the European’s union’s ERASMUS+ programme under the grant agreement number 612361 EUTOPIA 2050.

2. Researcher mobility programme

2.1. Overview

The Researcher Mobility pilot programme aims at reinforcing research collaboration through short-term, project-based research visits of EUTOPIA researchers and EUTOPIA international partners, in physical-mobility.

The program implementation is guided by two principles:

- Open and easily accessible program: lightweight application procedure, possibility to apply on-the-fly, quick answers;
- Decentralized implementation: local program referents in each partner institution offer a direct contact for researchers.

The open call for this programme has been launched in July 2020 and advertised on websites and through internal communication (see Appendix 2).

Due to the Covid sanitary crisis, researcher mobility plan had to be postponed and the programme did not have a lot of immediate interest for the researchers.

The call was advertised and presented also during the EUTOPIA WEEKS: First in November 2020, during the EUTOPIA week organized by the University of Warwick² and then in April 2021, during EUTOPIA week organized by the university of Gothenborg³. After this second event, all EUTOPIA partners launched a second wave of dissemination of the call information within the research community with internal e-mailings.

2.2. Application and selection process

Researchers from EUTOPIA universities and their international partner universities, cooperating with EUTOPIA research teams (Kyungpook National University (KNU, South Korea), Monash University (Australia), International University of Rabat (Morocco), Stellenbosch University (South Africa)) are eligible to this pilot programme.

All *EUTOPIA Research Mobility* visits should be **centered on a research & innovation project** which may contribute to the EUTOPIA alliance building.

² <https://warwick.ac.uk/global/partnerships/europe/eutopia/eutopia-week#itinerary>

³ https://gu-se.zoom.us/webinar/register/WN_gF7-Wou5SgOHj6AzAgbe6g

The application and selection of projects to the *EUTOPIA Research Mobility Program* are jointly managed by the local program managers (LPM) of the applicant's home and host institutions. All the application and selection details are described in the call text (see Appendix 1).

The local selection process is be under the authority of the institutions' representative in charge of the EUTOPIA Research Mobility Program (VP in charge of International Scientific Development, VP Research, etc.)

2.3. Implementation of the Researcher Mobility Programme

The *EUTOPIA Research Mobility Program* is be implemented in a decentralized manner, by local program managers (LPM) in each partner university and coordinated by CY Cergy Paris University.

The LPMs represents Research support/research support, Grants and innovation or EUTOPIA offices and Institutes of advanced studies in each university. They will be the main contact point for the researchers providing all the necessary information regarding the implementation of the mobilities (travel, accommodation, local host contacts, etc.).

The LPM of the Home and the Host university coordinate in order to take care of the proper implementation of each visit. The host researchers will also be involved in the process in close connection with the LPM.

Each university will finance at least 2 researcher mobilities under EUTOPIA TRAIN project. These mobilities will complement the previous 24 mobilities expected within the frame of EUTOPIA 2050 project.

2.4. Work programme and output of the Researcher mobility programme

The researchers involved in the Researcher's mobility programme will represent a probe in EUTOPIA research community to identify and build the research collaboration network.

This pilot programme and the visits will provide the following inputs to the LPM:

- after each visit, the researchers will fill the research visit logs
- and within 1 month a short report describing the visits and the expected outcomes

The reporting documents will be provided by the coordination team (CYU) to the LPM.

The reporting material is available in appendix 3.

The management team will collect the logs and reports from all the LPM.

This material will contribute to build:

- a living collaboration mapping (from June 2021 with the collaboration status before the mobility programmes implementation, to the end of the project with an expected more targeted scheme),
- analysis for the TRAIN management board and input for TRAIN WP1 in charge of developing the EUTOPIA common research and innovation agenda, identifying bottom-up collaboration opportunities and potential EUTOPIA research networks.

3. Young Leader Academy

3.1. Overview

As part of the EUTOPIA 2050 and EUTOPIA-TRAIN projects, the EUTOPIA Alliance is committed to developing a new initiative, the EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy (YLA), aimed at promoting career perspectives, scientific exchange and research impact for high potential early- to mid-career researchers.

The ambition of the EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy (YLA) is to promote career perspectives and support research exchanges between high-potential, early to mid-career researchers, coming from all EUTOPIA partner universities. Members of the EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy will constitute a community of promising independent research leaders at the scale of EUTOPIA, sharing and promoting European values and the EUTOPIA vision of an interconnected academic environment.

EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy Fellows will be given the opportunity:

- To develop their research leadership skills through a dedicated training program;
- To take part in interdisciplinary scholarly exchange and research networking activities, among Fellows and with the broader EUTOPIA research community;
- To initiate research collaborations within the EUTOPIA Alliance
- To contribute to the development of a challenge-based and student-shaped curriculum, through the development of research-led learning units open to undergraduate and graduate students;
- To act as EUTOPIA ambassadors, contributing to the Alliance's activities and fostering the emergence of an integrated research community at the EUTOPIA scale. Common research agenda

The internal call has been launched on April 30th 2021 and closed on June 30th 2021 and advertised on EUTOPIA websites and by internal e-mailings (see Appendix 2).

3.2. Application and selection process

The applicants, early to mid-career researchers, formally appointed with one of the Universities of the EUTOPIA Alliance should hold a tenured or tenure-track position or major research fellowship. This may ensure that they are already in a position of being a research leader in the EUTOPIA alliance.

The YLA fellows will represent the most promising leaders at the scale of EUTOPIA with ambitious transdisciplinary research objectives serving as EUTOPIA alliance ambassadors.

The application and selection process, described in Appendix 1, will be locally managed by Local Programme managers (LPM) for a first shortlisting of candidates.

The final list of selected fellows will be under the authority of the YLA steering committee which will take into account gender and disciplinary balance.

3.3. Implementation of the YLA

The YLA programme will be implemented at 3 levels:

-The **EUTOPIA level** with a Steering Committee responsible for:

- the scientific seminars and their chairing aiming to contribute to the interdisciplinary and challenge driven research agenda (2 annual meetings, monthly e-seminars, scientific workshops)
- the supervision of the YLA contribution in bridging the gap between science and the rest of society, participating in the EUTOPIA Open and Citizen science activities,
- the training content definition.

The chairing of the Steering committee will rotate periodically.

The Steering Committee is composed of academic leads appointed by each university (Institute of Advanced studies director or deputy director, Vice rector for research or knowledge transfer, head of research offices.), Local Program Managers from each University of the Alliance (see below) and the coordination team of CY Cergy Paris University.

-The **local level** with the Local Programme Managers (LPM), representing European liaison/ Research support Grant and Innovation / International Scientific Development offices, Research and Development centres or Institutes of Advanced Studies. In addition to the management of the application and selection procedures, they will represent the major contact points for the YLA fellows, especially when the mobilities for individual research visits will be concerned or when events will have to be organized locally. They will also, together with the coordination team, support the YLA fellows in the organization of their research-led and challenge-based training modules open to undergraduate and graduate students.

-The **overall coordination level** will be represented by the coordination team of CY Cergy Paris University. The coordination team will manage the YLA training and seminar calendar and collect the YLA fellows' reports (see Appendix 3 for reporting material details) and inputs for EUTOPIA TRAIN and 2050 projects activities. The coordination team will also manage the communication activities related to the YLA which will start with the creation of a dedicated webpage for and with the fellows. The webpage will gather scientific communication and citizen science activities.

12 YLA fellows will be appointed for a 2 years programme under the EUTOPIA 2050 project and 6 more under EUTOPIA TRAIN project.

The YLA activities will start in September 2021.

3.4. YLA training programme

The EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy will offer the following activities to the selected fellows:

- Networking activities and scholarly exchanges
- Skill development and training activities;

- Visits aimed at acquainting the Fellows with the research environment of the universities of the EUTOPIA Alliance

The detailed program of activities will be defined by the YLA steering committee with the active participation of YLA Fellows. As the selection process will be finalized in July 2021, the fellows background and expectations are not yet known and the Steering committee is willing to build this first training programme in a bottom-up perspective.

The programme should target the very early-stage fellows with the training seminars and provide more tailored events to the most advanced ones.

The programme will mix the following four type of activities:

The YLA kick-off

The kick off meeting of each cohort will be organized at the beginning of the training, using as much as possible the opportunity of a back-to-back event with the EUTOPIA weeks.

The event will enable the fellows to better know each other's, meet the YLA Steering committee, the Local programme managers and the coordination team. The EUTOPIA week context will be also very important start they training as EUTOPIA Ambassadors.

An inspiring keynote speech may be delivered to welcome the fellows.

The kick-off meeting may preferably occur in a physical format.

Training activities

The YLA programme will propose training sessions in seminar format for skill development and training activities.

These activities will focus on tools and methods that are directly and individually applicable by YLA Fellows in their role as research leaders. The program will take into Fellows' needs and suggestions and may include:

- Skills in scientific and scholarly leadership
- Team and research project management
- Personal research network development
- Interdisciplinary approaches in research
- Grant applications
- Scientific communication
- Innovation and impact, including IP management
- Open Science and Fair data

The training activities will be built on different inputs from:

- The needs identified directly by the fellows, expressed in a survey they will have to answer as soon as they will be selected,
- EUTOPIA TRAIN WP2 for innovation and entrepreneurship,

- EUTOPIA TRAIN WP3 for all the tools and activities related to open science, open access and citizen science,
- EUTOPIA TRAIN WP4.3 for all the training concerning leadership and team management from the Human resource point of view,
- EUTOPIA TRAIN WP5 for all the necessary in-depth trainings on IP management, Ethics, Research project management and funding

The training sessions may be proposed on a bi-monthly frequency.

The training sessions may be mostly online or hybrid and also in get together format, especially when occurring in the frame of the kick off meeting timeframe.

YLA yearly Symposium

The Symposium will be centered on a broad cross-cutting theme and jointly organized by the YLA and the fellows. The symposium will be open to all EUTOPIA and external stakeholders.

The YLA Symposium may be organized between June and September each year.

The Symposiums will hopefully be physical get together meetings.

E-seminars: Workshops and research groups

Workshops and research groups, on specific theme or topics, will be organized regularly by the fellows and may involve other EUTOPIA researchers or invited persons.

A monthly base will be suggested to the fellows for these short events.

The e-seminars will mostly be online or hybrid using the visits each fellow will make within EUTOPIA as an opportunity for stimulate the cohort cohesion and interaction.

Previsionnal calendar of the 2021-2023 programme

- Kick-off meeting: November 2021 (back-to-back with the Barcelona EUTOPIA week)
- Training sessions (may be rescheduled and adapted after the fellow's expectations):
 - November 2021: Kick-off event. External engagement – Open Science
 - January 2022: Impact and innovation
 - March 2022: Leadership in research and in team management
 - May 2022: Research funding
 - September 2022: Personal research development network
 - November 2022: Social networks: YLA2.0
 - ...
- E-Seminar: Starts November 2021 to June 2023 on a monthly frequency
- By February 2022: fellows will be asked to submit:
 - Their plan of activities including research collaboration plan or workshop organization
 - Their proposal for one learning unit (together with at least another fellow)

4. Appendix

4.1. Appendix 1-Call description

4.1.1. Researcher mobility call text

EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Program

Call for applications and programme description

Updated version: April 2021

Open call, launched July 2020

Background and overview

The EUTOPIA Alliance is pleased to announce the launch of the *EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Programme*.

The [EUTOPIA Alliance](#) is a network of six universities that was awarded an Erasmus+ ‘European Universities’ pilot project in 2019 and officially launched in December 2019:

- [University of Warwick](#)
- [Vrije Universiteit Brussel](#)
- [CY Cergy Paris University](#)
- [University of Ljubljana](#)
- [Pompeu Fabra University](#)
- [University of Gothenburg](#)

The core mission of the *EUTOPIA Alliance* is to promote a connected and inclusive academic community, addressing global and local challenges, advancing excellence and inclusion, geared towards impact and fostering European economic development and innovation through a deep engagement of the Alliance with its local and regional ecosystems. The promotion of scientific excellence, research collaboration and mobility of academics among the partner universities is a core objective of EUTOPIA.

The partner universities therefore launch the joint *EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Program*.

Objectives of the program

The *EUTOPIA Research Mobility Program* supports short research visits for EUTOPIA researchers across partner universities in order to foster collaboration and integration, to share expertise and research infrastructures and to develop **joint research activities** (e.g. common publication, supervision of PhD co-tutelles, joint applications for external research funds etc.).

In order to create productive links between academics of the EUTOPIA alliance, all visits in the scope of the *Research Mobility Program* must be **project-led**. The projects shall be carried out at the host institution during the visit in collaboration with a **host researcher** within this institution.

The *EUTOPIA Research Mobility Program* is open to **all academic disciplines and topics**, while the EUTOPIA overarching theme “Planetary well-being” shall be promoted within the program and projects related to this theme are encouraged.

Visits are funded for duration of **2 to 3 weeks** and be compensated as **outgoing research mobility** by the researcher’s home institution, in the limit of 3 000€ per visit.

Research visits should take place before November 2022.

The program implementation is guided by two principles:

- **Open and easily accessible program**: lightweight application procedure, possibility to apply on-the-fly, quick answers;
- **Decentralized implementation**: local program referents in each partner institution offer a direct contact for researchers.

Application and selection process

The application and selection of projects to the *EUTOPIA Research Mobility Program* are jointly managed by the local program referents of the applicant’s home and host institutions (part 4 and 6).

Who can apply:

- a) **Faculty from all EUTOPIA partner universities**, including post-doctoral fellows.
- b) **Faculty from other international partner institutions** cooperating with a EUTOPIA research team.

Pre-doctoral researchers are not covered by this mobility program (but are eligible for a separate dedicated doctoral mobility scheme, in preparation).

A minimum of 3/4 of the visiting fellowships is dedicated to EUTOPIA faculty (EUTOPIA universities’ employees) and up to 1/4 can be given to faculty coming from outside the EUTOPIA network, under the condition of having an ongoing cooperation with a EUTOPIA university (other than the institution hosting the planned *Research Mobility Program* visit) linked to the visit.

Requirements:

All *EUTOPIA Research Mobility* visits must be **centered on a research project**, such as:

- a) A classical research project (focus on scientific objectives),
- b) An innovation project (focus on R&D, innovation and technology transfer) or
- c) A project focusing on the utilization of research results and their application in socio-economic environments.

In the case of a *EUTOPIA Research Mobility* linked to an ongoing research project between partner universities financed by external sources, such as H2020 etc., applicants must make sure that the EUTOPIA Research Mobility funds can be combined with the regular project financing. They can refer their home institution's local program referent for more information.

Both the **visiting fellow** and the **host researcher** shall be actively implicated in the project's realization during the visit.

How to apply:

Applicants submit the **EUTOPIA Research Mobility Program application form**:

- a) Applicants from EUTOPIA partner universities submit the form to the *local program referents of his/her home and host institution*: in a single email addressed to both referents;
- b) Applicants from other international partners institutions submit the form to the *local program referent of his/her host institution*, per email.

The application must include (within the application form):

- a pre-defined research project, to be carried out during the visit;
- the nomination of a host researcher co-responsible for the research project during the visit; he/she shall also be the first contact person for the visiting fellow in the host institution for the preparation of the visit and during the stay;
- the counter-signature of the director of the host research center, confirming the research center's capacity of offering good research conditions and office space during the visit;

Only applicants from other international partner institutions (not EUTOPIA universities) submit, additionally, a support letter from the EUTOPIA member university holding the research cooperation with the applicant, stating the ongoing cooperation and the interest of the applicant's EUTOPIA Research Mobility for this cooperation.

When to apply:

- The application process will **open on 6 July 2020**
- **Applications can be submitted continuously** from this date on and until depletion of the dedicated mobility funds (part 5)
- **Research visits should take place before November 2022.**

In the current circumstances of COVID 19 prevention, applicants need to take into account eventual travel restriction when submitting their application, in order to provide for travel dates which does not fall into periods of mobility restriction.

Selection process:

For applications from EUTOPIA faculty, a joint selection process is operated by the applicant's home and host universities:

- Check of the application's eligibility by the local program referents;
- Validation/refusal of the application by the institutions' representative in charge of the *EUTOPIA Research Mobility Program* (VP in charge of International Scientific Development, VP Research, etc.);
- Coordination between the program referents for joint validation/refusal of the proposal: if both institutional representatives accept the application, it is validated. If one refuses, it is refused.
- Communication of the result to the applicant by his/her home institution's program referent (within 2 weeks after reception of the application)⁴. This should include a feedback on the strengths (in case of validation) and weaknesses (in case of refusal) of the project in regards to the program objectives. Refused projects can be resubmitted.

For applications by faculty from other international partners institutions, the selection process is identical, with the sole difference that it implicates the host institution's program referent and representative only.

Selection criteria:

The objective of the *EUTOPIA Research Mobility Program* is to contribute to the dynamics of a stimulating and interactive EUTOPIA research environment, including all topics and disciplines, with a special focus on the overarching theme "Planetary well-being".

In line with the overarching theme, EUTOPIA encourages projects linked to UN Sustainable Development Goals (<https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/sdgs>) and contributing to major societal questions. 5 specific themes have been identified for research collaboration which can also guide the development of *EUTOPIA Research Mobility* projects: (a) welfare and inclusion, (b) materials, (c) artificial intelligence, (d) health, and (e) sustainability.

More generally, it is expected from the research visits to either launch or reinforce research cooperation between EUTOPIA institutions on an individual (researchers), intermediate (teams/medium scale projects) or institutional level (research centers/large scale projects).

EUTOPIA Research Mobility proposals will be assessed against the above-mentioned criteria, with a special attention to:

⁴ Exception made for vacation periods, such as in August or End of December. Delays for an answer will be longer in these periods.

- A well-defined research project for the duration of the visit (i.e. definition of a challenge to be tackled, objectives to be attained, cooperation dynamic to be reinforced);
- The support of the project by a host researcher and a host research center;
- The expected outcomes of the mobility visit and next collaboration steps planned after the visit.

Implementation of the research mobility

The *EUTOPIA Research Mobility Program* will be implemented in a decentralized manner, by local program referents in each partner university (part 6) responsible for:

- the promotion of the program among its academic communities,
- the application and selection process,
- the program implementation.

Program implementation:

- Outgoing/incoming mobility: selected *EUTOPIA Research Mobility* projects submitted by EUTOPIA faculty are **financed by the researchers' home university** according to the university's general procedure for *outgoing research mobility*. Projects submitted by faculty from other international partner institutions are **financed by the researchers' host institution** according to the university's general procedure for *incoming research mobility*.

Issues such as health/accident insurance coverage and other practical aspects regarding the researchers' visits (e.g. visa, if applicable, etc.) remain the sole responsibility of the researcher, according to the above-mentioned procedures of the home and host institutions for researcher mobility.

- Financing modalities & expenditure: following the above-mentioned principles, each university applies its own modalities for financing the *EUTOPIA Research Mobility* visits, as well as its table for mobility expenditure. Expenditure in the scope of the *EUTOPIA Research Mobility* include accommodation and living expenses during the stay, as well as travel expenses, in the limit of 3000 euros per visit (total costs). According to each university's functioning, the institution may assist the researcher in the organization of his/her research visit and directly pay the travel and accommodation costs, or ask the researcher to organize these aspects in order to be reimbursed by the institution.

Each university details its rules for mobility financing in a note "PRACTICAL MODALITIES OF THE EUTOPIA RESEARCH MOBILITY PROGRAM", made available to candidates by the local program referent. The note includes details regarding the organization of the stay (assistance by the institution or organization by the researcher for reimbursement) and possibly additional expenditure restrictions, if applicable.

- Host institutions' services: the visiting fellow's main contact person in the host institution is his/her host researcher. The host researcher shall help with the preparation of the visit, particularly for practical aspects regarding office space and access to research facilities in the host research center during the stay, as well as with internal services, and guide the visiting fellow during his/her stay. The host institution's program referent can assist the host researcher for practical questions. Reasonable and bona fide costs of the research carried out as part of the mobility project will be financed by the host research center (material, tools, machines etc.).
- Visiting fellow's obligations: the visiting fellow must abide by all rules and obligations of the host university which affects him/her during the stay, such as safety, use of facilities, code of conduct, etc. Each visiting fellow is expected to prepare a short report on his/her research mobility on the basis of a template to be sent to him/her by the program referent of his/her home (EUTOPIA faculty) or host institution (other international faculty) and submit it 4 weeks after the end of his/her stay to the program referent.

Each university wishing to clarify rules and obligations applying to incoming visiting fellows detail these in a note "RULES AND OBLIGATIONS FOR THE EUTOPIA RESEARCH MOBILITY PROGRAM", made available to the candidates by the local program referents.

Program budget / number of Visiting Fellows

- EUTOPIA budget for the program (EU funds): 72K€
- EUTOPIA Budget per partner institution (EU funds): 12K€

According to the up-mentioned budget and the maximum amount of 3 000€ per visit (part 4), **each institution can finance a minimum of 4 research mobility projects**. However, depending on each university's table for mobility expenditure, the number of financed mobility projects can vary slightly between the partners.

A first assessment of the program will be realized in December 2020. According to the success of the program in each institution, the partners shall be allowed to consider reallocation of parts of the funds between the partner institutions by mutual agreement, at the earliest six months after the launch of the program. Additional budget can also be made available on the bases of universities' own contributions or additional funds coming from new EU calls for European Universities.

Contacts

In order to get an overview on the research activity within the EUTOPIA partner institutions and establish the contact with individual researchers or research centers of partner institutions, please refer to the following links:

- University of Warwick: <https://warwick.ac.uk/research/>
- Vrije Universiteit Brussel: <https://www.vub.be/en/research;>

- CY Cergy Paris University: <http://theparisseineinitiative.org/en/research-areas-and-research-centers/> and <https://www.u-cergy.fr/en/research.html>
- University of Ljubljana: https://www.uni-lj.si/research_and_development/
- Pompeu Fabra University: <https://www.upf.edu/web/guest/research>
- University of Gothenburg: <https://www.gu.se/english/research/?languageId=100001&disableRedirect=true&returnUrl=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.gu.se%2Fforskning%2F>

Local referents of the *EUTOPIA Research Mobility* program, in charge of the application / selection procedure and practical questions about the program, are:

- *University of Warwick*: Institute of Advanced Study, IAS@Warwick.ac.uk
- *Vrije Universiteit Brussel*: rd.secretariaat, rd.secretariaat@vub.be
- *CY Cergy Paris University*: Karine Gambier Leroy, Secretary General of the Institut for Advanced Studies, CY Cergy Paris University, karine.gambier-leroy@cyu.fr ;
- *University of Ljubljana*: Rebeka Lesjak, Research support advisor, University office for Research, University of Ljubljana, rebeka.lesjak@uni-lj.si
- *Pompeu Fabra University*: Mireia Calm, EUTOPIA Office, eutopia@upf.eu
- *University of Gothenburg*: Henrik Lindskog, Research Support Grants and Innovation Office, University of Gothenburg, henrik.lindskog@gu.se

Contact for general inquiries:

Sylvie Niessen, Director of International Scientific Development, CY Cergy Paris University, sylvie.niessen@cyu.fr

4.1.2. Young leader Academy call text

EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy

Call for applications and program description

Call opening: 30 April 2021

Call closing: 30 June 2021

Background and overview

The EUTOPIA Alliance is pleased to announce the launch of the *EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy*.

The [EUTOPIA Alliance](#) is a network of six universities that was awarded an Erasmus+ ‘European Universities’ pilot project in 2019 and officially launched in December 2019, gathering the [Vrije Universiteit Brussel](#), [CY Cergy Paris University](#), the [University of Gothenburg](#), the [University of Ljubljana](#), [Pompeu Fabra University](#) and the [University of Warwick](#)

The core mission of the *EUTOPIA Alliance* is to promote a connected and inclusive academic community, addressing global and local challenges, advancing excellence and inclusion, geared towards impact and fostering European economic development and innovation through a deep engagement of the Alliance with its local and regional ecosystems. The promotion of scientific excellence, research collaboration and mobility of academics among the partner universities is a core objective of EUTOPIA.

The ambition of the EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy (YLA) is to support research exchanges between high-potential, early to mid-career researchers, coming from all EUTOPIA partner universities and to support their career development. Members of the EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy will constitute a community of promising independent research leaders at the scale of EUTOPIA, sharing and promoting European values and the EUTOPIA vision of an interconnected academic environment.

Objectives of the program

The main objectives of the Young Leaders Academy are:

1. To promote **research excellence in all academic fields**– Through dedicated training programs, the Young Leaders Academy will offer its Fellows the opportunity to reinforce their scientific leadership and project management skills and enhance their research network. It will also offer them a platform to valorise their research projects and results within the EUTOPIA Alliance and beyond;
2. To develop **scientific exchange and research collaborations** among YLA Fellows and with the larger EUTOPIA research community. By organizing dedicated scientific events, as well as networking and training sessions, the Young Leaders Academy facilitates the emergence of

- an integrated cohort of promising researchers actively contributing to the dynamic of the Alliance and catalysing collaborative research projects between EUTOPIA partners;
3. To advance an **interdisciplinary and challenge-driven research** agenda allowing YLA Fellows to address the major scientific and societal issues of our time, in accordance with EUTOPIA's central mission to promote a connected and inclusive academic community, addressing global and local challenges and geared towards impact. The Young Leaders Academy is open to all disciplines and promotes, *inter alia*, research addressing six key research areas and societal issues: (a) Welfare and Inclusion, (b) Materials Engineering, (c) Data & Intelligence, (d) Health, e) Sustainability, (f) Culture & Heritage.
 4. To bridge the gap between science and society by encouraging fellows to endorse Open Science principles and to engage external stakeholders, citizens, as well as local and regional ecosystems.
 5. To contribute to the broader objectives of the EUTOPIA Alliance, to promote a student-shaped, research and challenge-driven integrated academic community, as emphasized in the EUTOPIA 2050 project

The YLA will draw on similar initiatives developed in different contexts⁵. In comparison with other programs, the EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy offers two distinctive features: the twofold objective of offering leadership training and promoting scientific exchange and collaboration; the promotion of the program at the scale of the EUTOPIA Alliance, rather than in a single university.

EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy Fellows will be given the opportunity:

- To develop their research leadership skills through a dedicated training program;
- To take part in interdisciplinary scholarly exchange and research networking activities, among Fellows and with the broader EUTOPIA research community;
- To initiate research collaborations within the EUTOPIA Alliance
- To contribute to the development of a challenge-based and student-shaped curriculum, through the development of research-led learning units open to undergraduate and graduate students;
- To act as EUTOPIA ambassadors, contributing to the Alliance's activities and fostering the emergence of an integrated research community at the EUTOPIA scale. Common research agenda

Program activities

Overview

The EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy will offer the following activities:

⁵ Examples of similar initiatives can be found at [Cambridge University](#), [Aarhus University](#), the [Global Young Academy](#) or the [Tuks Young Research Leadership Program](#).

- Networking activities and scholarly exchanges
- Skill development and training activities;
- Visits aimed at acquainting the Fellows with the research environment of the universities of the EUTOPIA Alliance

The detailed program of activities will be defined by the YLA steering committee, composed of academic leads and program managers from each University of the Alliance, with the active participation of YLA Fellows.

Skill development and training activities

The skill development and training activities will focus on tools and methods that are directly and individually applicable by YLA Fellows in their role as research leaders. The program will take into Fellows' needs and suggestions and include:

- Skills in scientific and scholarly leadership
- Team and research project management
- Personal research network development
- Interdisciplinary approaches in research
- Grant applications
- Scientific communication
- Innovation and impact, including IP management
- Open Science and Fair data

Scientific exchange and networking activities

Scientific exchange and networking activities will include:

- **Dedicated YLA annual meetings**
These meetings will offer a forum for exchanges amongst fellows and with the broader EUTOPIA scholarly community and will promote interdisciplinary approaches to key challenges of our time through open research presentations and themed sessions. With the core participation of YLA Fellows, these meetings may also be open to other researchers from the EUTOPIA scientific community, in connection with the EUTOPIA week and other EUTOPIA activities.
- **YLA monthly e-seminar**
Throughout the academic year, the monthly online seminar will be dedicated to presentations of their research by the YLA Fellows for the YLA Fellows. The program of the seminar will be advertised across the Alliance and attendance to the sessions will be open to other researchers from the Alliance to foster exposure and integration of the Fellows.

In addition to these activities, Fellows will be offered the possibility to undertake **individual research visits to other universities of the EUTOPIA Alliance**, related to their individual research project, funded through a dedicated mobility budget. The EUTOPIA Young Leader Academy may also support groups of Fellows in the organization of scientific workshop.

YLA Fellows conditions of appointment

- The EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy will enroll a first cohort of 18 Fellows, starting in September 2021. A second call for applications is scheduled to open in early 2023, with the possibility of enrolling a new cohort.
- Duration of appointment:
 - YLA Fellows are appointed for a period of 2 years.
- Conditions of appointment:
 - Fellows are offered dedicated leadership training and high-level networking opportunities;
 - Fellows are offered a dedicated mobility budget of 5k€ for the duration of their appointment. This mobility budget may be supplemented by additional contributions from their home university. Fellows are also funded for their participation in YLA activities. They may request additional financial support for the organization of scientific activities and workshops;
 - Depending on their Home university, Fellows may be eligible to additional benefits;
 - In the development of their research funding application and innovation projects, Fellows can receive support from the EUTOPIA Grants, Legal, and Innovation Office (GLENN)⁶.
- Commitments: Fellows commit to:
 - Attending YLA training sessions, networking and scientific events
 - Contributing to the development of collaborative research projects, joint proposals, common publications, scientific event organization etc. with other YLA Fellows and/or other researchers from the EUTOPIA Alliance
 - Contributing to the development of one EUTOPIA research-led learning unit
 - Extensively representing the EUTOPIA Alliance, aims and achievements in internal and external EUTOPIA community-building events and acting as EUTOPIA ambassadors
 - Acting as a user group for other EUTOPIA initiatives such as the design of GLENN offices,
 - Sharing their newly acquired leadership skills and experience of YLA with EUTOPIA community and the next YLA cohort

Application and selection process

Eligible applicants

- Applicants should be formally appointed with one of the Universities of the EUTOPIA Alliance and hold a tenured or tenure-track position or major research fellowship;
- Application to the Young Leaders Academy is open to early to mid-career researchers, preferably between 2 to 12 years after PhD completion⁷;
- Career breaks will be considered for the extension of the eligibility window in the case of parental leave, long- term illness and national service after PhD award;

⁶ The EUTOPIA Grants, Legal, and Innovation Office (GLENN) is developed under the EUTOPIA-TRAIN project.

⁷ This corresponds to ERC Starting and Consolidator levels

- Applicants are expected to demonstrate leadership potential as attested by their academic track record (incl. research management, coordination and supervision) and ambitious academic career development plan.

Application procedure

- Candidates shall submit a full application, composed of:
 - The YLA application form, which can be downloaded on the program's main page (link below) and which includes:
 - A summary of past research achievements and on-going research agenda;
 - A discussion of the motivation for joining the Young Leader Academy, including training expectations, planned research collaborations, expected contribution to the Young Leaders Academy and the EUTOPIA Alliance (workshop organization, possible contribution to learning units, role of EUTOPIA Ambassador, etc.)
 - A detailed academic CV
 - Support letters from the Head of Department and Head of Research group of the applicant.
- Applications must be sent by email before **30 June 2021** to the Local Program Manager of the applicant's Home university (see the list of program managers below)

Selection procedure

- Each EUTOPIA University shall select 3 candidates for appointment as Fellow of the EUTOPIA Young Leader Academy, under the present call.
- The selection procedure will be implemented in a decentralized manner, using common evaluation criteria emphasizing the relevance of the YLA appointment for (i) the Fellow, (ii) the Young Leaders Academy, (iii) the EUTOPIA Alliance. The composition of the selection committee will be decided internally by each university.
- The selection will aim for gender parity and a diversity of research domains, seniority and backgrounds.

Contact and information

Local managers of the EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy, in charge of the application and selection procedure and practical questions about the program, are:

- *Vrije Universiteit Brussel*: Cristina Macovei, R&D European liaison office, Cristina.Macovei@vub.be
- *CY Cergy Paris University*: Kate Robinson, International Scientific Development Office, katy.robinson@cyu.fr
- *University of Ljubljana*: Polona Juvancic, Research and Development Centre, polona.juvancic@uni-lj.si
- *Pompeu Fabra University*: María Gil, European Projects Manager & Research Advisor, maria.gil@upf.edu
- *University of Gothenburg*: Henrik Lindskog, Research Support Grants and Innovation Office, henrik.lindskog@gu.se
- *University of Warwick*: John Burden, Institute of Advanced Studies, j.p.burden@warwick.ac.uk

4.2. Appendix 2-Screenshots & links for communication

4.2.1. Researcher mobility programme screenshots & links

The open call for this programme has been launched in July 2020 and advertised by the following means:

-EUTOPIA website (<https://eutopia-university.eu/2020/06/23/eutopia-researcher-mobility-program/>)

EUTOPIA EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY

ALLIANCE - WORKING GROUPS - OPPORTUNITIES - STUDENTS - NEWS - CONTACTS

EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Program

OPEN CALL LAUNCHED on 6th July 2020

The objective of Researcher Mobility Program is to support research visits of EUTOPIA researchers across EUTOPIA partner universities, in order to foster research collaborations and to allow the sharing of expertise and infrastructures and the development of joint research activities (e.g. common publications, PhD co-tutoring, joint applications for external research funds etc.), in line with EUTOPIA's mission to promote a connected and inclusive academic community, addressing global and local challenges and advancing excellence and inclusion.

The programme is developed as part of the EUTOPIA *europa Erasmus+* project. It will allow each EUTOPIA university to finance a minimum of 4 research mobility projects, for a total of **24 research visits** over the duration of the EUTOPIA 2020 project.

All visits financed under the EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Program should be **project-led** and allow the development and furthering of research collaborations between the researchers of the EUTOPIA Alliance. The program is open to all **academic disciplines and topics**. Projects addressing key societal challenges of our time, and related to EUTOPIA's overarching theme "Planetary well-being" are especially encouraged.

APPLICATIONS TO THE EUTOPIA RESEARCHER MOBILITY PROGRAMME CAN NOW BE SUBMITTED

- by EUTOPIA researchers to the local programme manager of their home institution
- by researchers from international partner universities, outside of EUTOPIA, to the local programme manager of their host institution

IF YOU ARE INTERESTED IN APPLYING, PLEASE CONSULT THE DOCUMENTS BELOW:

COMPLETE CALL DESCRIPTION [\(link\)](#)

APPLICATION FORM [\(link\)](#)

LOCAL PROGRAM MANAGERS

Wijze Universiteit Brussel: secretariaat, rs@secretariaat@vub.be

CY Cergy Paris University: Karine Gambier Leroy, Secretary General of the Institut for Advanced Studies, CY Cergy Paris University, karine.gambier-leroy@cyu.fr

University of Gothenburg: Henrik Lindskog, Research Support Grants and Innovation Office, University of Gothenburg, henrik.lindskog@gu.se

University of Ljubljana: Rebeka Lenjak, Research support advisor, University office for Research, University of Ljubljana, rebeka.lenjak@uni-lj.si

Pontepaulebra University: Miria Calm, EUTOPIA Office, eutopia@upf.edu

University of Warwick: Institute of Advanced Study, IAS@Warwick.ac.uk

CONTACT FOR GENERAL INQUIRIES

Sylvie Niessen, Director of International Scientific Development, CY Cergy Paris University, sylvie.niessen@cyu.fr

What's new

EUTOPIA University Retweeted

The Covid @covid19

The Covid member universities emphasize that collaboration within the #EUTOPIAuniversities initiative needs to go full-on, based on the efficient, disruptive strategies.

See our recommendations [#EUTOPIACALL](#)

Retweeted by The Netherlands Young Researcher European University Alliance

May 21, 2021

EUTOPIA University Retweeted

WUB @EUTOPIAcall

On 28 May, we commemorate the official birthday of our university. We do this by highlighting the social commitment of our students and staff active students speak out. One of them is @RenataCh. She studies Social Sciences at the WUB and fights for a better world. #TheWorldNeedsYou

May 20, 2021

EUTOPIA Facebook

Eutopia European ... 873 likes

Ready to become a Young Leader Fellow at the EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy? Supporting research exchanges between high-potential, early to mid-

Translate

Select language or locale

Powered by Google Translation

- The EUTOPIA universities websites relay the information:

CY Advanced Studies: (<https://iea.u-cergy.fr/fr/financements-et-appels-a-projets/eutopia-researcher-mobility-program.html>)

iea.u-cergy.fr/fr/financements-et-appels-a-projets/eutopia-researcher-mobility-program.html

Financements et appels à projets / EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Program

EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Program

08.07.2020 - 30.06.2021

Le programme *EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility* a pour objectif de renforcer les coopérations scientifiques au sein de l'alliance EUTOPIA qui réunit les universités suivantes :

- Vrije Universiteit Brussel,
- University of Gothenburg,
- University of Ljubljana,
- Universitat Pompeu Fabra,
- University of Warwick.

Le programme est ouvert à toutes les disciplines et à tous les thèmes de recherche. Les projets portant sur les principaux défis sociétaux de notre époque et liés au thème général d'EUTOPIA "Le bien-être planétaire" sont particulièrement encouragés.

Le programme est ouvert aux chercheurs de toutes les universités partenaires d'EUTOPIA, y compris les postdocs, et aux chercheurs des partenaires internationaux des six universités d'EUTOPIA, dans le cadre de projets de recherche impliquant des chercheurs de plusieurs universités membres d'EUTOPIA.

- Le programme permet le financement de séjours de recherche de courte durée (2 à 3 semaines) et couvre les frais de transport, d'hébergement ainsi que les repas et le transport intérieur pendant le séjour, dans la limite de 3000 euros par projet.
- Pour les chercheurs EUTOPIA, les conditions de remboursement seront définies conformément aux règles financières de l'université d'origine du chercheur. Pour les professeurs internationaux, les règles financières de l'université d'accueil s'appliqueront.

Une description complète de la procédure de candidature sera mise en ligne sur le site web d'EUTOPIA : plus d'informations [ici](#).

Warwick University: <https://warwick.ac.uk/global/partnerships/europe/eutopia/fundingop>

warwick.ac.uk/global/partnerships/europe/eutopia/fundingop

If you have any questions, please contact m.haymes@warwick.ac.uk

EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Programme

The **Researcher Mobility Programme** supports **research visits of EUTOPIA researchers across EUTOPIA partner universities**. The main objective of this program is to foster research collaborations and to allow the sharing of expertise and infrastructures and the development of joint research activities (e.g. common publications, PhD co-tutelles, joint applications for external research funds etc.), in line with EUTOPIA's mission to promote a connected and inclusive academic community, addressing global and local challenges and advancing excellence and inclusion.

The program is developed as part of the EUTOPIA 2050 Erasmus+ project. It allowed each EUTOPIA university to finance a minimum of 4 research mobility projects, for a total of **24 research visits** over the duration of the EUTOPIA 2050 project.

All visits financed under the EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Program should be **project-led** and allow the development and furthering of research collaborations between the researchers of the EUTOPIA Alliance. The program is open to **all academic disciplines and topics**. Projects addressing key societal challenges of our time, and related to EUTOPIA's overarching theme "Planetary well-being" are especially encouraged.

Further information, including a link to the application form and details of how to apply, can be found [here](#).

University of Pompeu Fabra:

<https://www.upf.edu/web/eutopia/research>

Eutopia

[The project](#) | [Work packages](#) | [Open Innovation Challenge](#) | [Educational Model](#) | [Become a Eutopia ambassador](#) | [Careers](#) | [Actions](#)

- Students
- Research

/ Actions / Research

Research

- EUTOPIA-SIF Science & Innovation Post-Doctoral Fellowships programme
- EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Program. Call: 6th July 2020

Objectives

The Researcher Mobility Program will support research visits of EUTOPIA researchers across EUTOPIA partner universities. The main objective of this program is to foster research collaborations and to allow the sharing of expertise and infrastructures and the development of joint research activities (e.g. common publications, PhD co-tutelles, joint applications for external research funds etc.), in line with EUTOPIA's mission to promote a connected and inclusive academic community, addressing global and local challenges and advancing excellence and inclusion.

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All visits financed under the EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Program should be project-led and allow the development and furthering of research collaborations between the researchers of the EUTOPIA Alliance. The program is open to all academic disciplines and topics. Projects addressing key societal challenges of our time, and related to EUTOPIA's overarching theme "Planetary well-being" are especially encouraged.

Eligibility and funding

Who can apply?

- o Faculty from all EUTOPIA partner universities, including post-doctoral fellows - Pre-doctoral researchers are not eligible to this mobility program (but a dedicated doctoral mobility program is in preparation).
- o Faculty from international partners of the six universities of EUTOPIA, within the frame of research projects involving researchers from multiple EUTOPIA member universities.

University of Ljubljana:

https://www.uni-lj.si/in_front/2020062311413024/

Univerza v Ljubljani

[STUDY](#) | [RESEARCH](#) | [QUALITY](#) | [DOCTORAL SCHOOL](#) | [ME](#)

> EUTOPIA RESEARCHER MOBILITY PROGRAM

UNILJ > in front

Publish Date: 23.06.2020
Category: News from the University

The Researcher Mobility Program will support research visits of EUTOPIA researchers across EUTOPIA partner universities. Launch of the call will be 6 July 2020.

Objectives

The main objective of this program is to foster research collaborations and to allow the sharing of expertise and infrastructures and the development of joint research activities (e.g. common publications, PhD co-tutelles, joint applications for external research funds etc.), in line with EUTOPIA's mission to promote a connected and inclusive academic community, addressing global and local challenges and advancing excellence and inclusion.

The program is developed as part of the EUTOPIA 2050 Erasmus+ project. It will allow each EUTOPIA university to finance a minimum of 4 research mobility projects, for a total of 24 research visits over the duration of the EUTOPIA 2050 project.

All visits financed under the EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Program should be **project-led** and allow the development and furthering of research collaborations between the researchers of the EUTOPIA Alliance. The program is open to **all academic disciplines and topics**. Projects addressing key societal challenges of our time, and related to EUTOPIA's overarching theme "Planetary well-being" are especially encouraged.

Eligibility and funding

Who can apply?

- o Faculty from all EUTOPIA partner universities, including post-doctoral fellows - Pre-doctoral researchers are not

Vrije Universiteit Brussel :

<https://research-funding.vub.be/projects/eutopia-researcher-mobility-program> (internal link)

EUTOPIA RESEARCHER MOBILITY PROGRAM.
LAST updated on: Tuesday 19 February 2021 - 11:23

Applications to the EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Program can now be submitted:

- by **EUTOPIA researchers** to the local program referents of their home institution,
- by **researchers from international partner universities**, outside of EUTOPIA, to the local program reference of their host institution

Please find below the details of the application procedure.

Local program referents' contact: RD.secretariat@vub.be - 7 32 2 529 2108

OBJECTIVES

The Researcher Mobility Program will support research visits of EUTOPIA researchers across EUTOPIA partner universities. The main objective of this program is to foster research collaborations and to allow the sharing of expertise and infrastructures and the development of joint research activities (e.g. common publications, PhD co-tutelles, joint applications for external research funds etc.), in line with EUTOPIA's mission to promote a connected and inclusive academic community, addressing global and local challenges and advancing excellence and inclusion.

The program is developed as part of the EUTOPIA 2050 Erasmus+ project. It will allow each EUTOPIA university to finance a minimum of 4 research mobility projects, for a total of **24 research visits** over the duration of the EUTOPIA 2050 project.

All visits financed under the EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Program should be **project-led** and allow the development and furthering of research collaborations between the researchers of the EUTOPIA Alliance. The program is open to **all academic disciplines and topics**. Projects addressing key societal challenges of our time, and related to EUTOPIA's overarching theme "Planetary well-being" are especially encouraged.

[+ More](#)

ATTACHEMENTS:

- + Practical Modalities VUB
- + Application Form

Attachment(s):
[Application Form EUTOPIA Researcher Mobility Programme](#)

- all the EUTOPIA universities had internal e-mailings to the researchers in order to advertise for the call

4.2.2. YLA programme screenshots & links

The YLA call, launched on 30 April 2021 and closed on 30 June 2021, has been advertised on the EUTOPIA website:

<https://eutopia-university.eu/young-leaders-academy/>

EUTOPIA EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY

ALLIANCE ▾ WORKING GROUPS ▾ OPPORTUNITIES ▾ STUDENTS ▾ NEWS ▾ CONTACTS ▾

Young Leaders Academy (YLA)

The ambition of the EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy (YLA) is to support research exchanges between high-potential, early to mid-career researchers from all EUTOPIA partner universities and support their career development.

Members of the EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy will constitute a community of promising independent research leaders at the scale of EUTOPIA, sharing and promoting European values and the EUTOPIA vision of an interconnected academic environment.

EUTOPIA Young Leaders Academy Fellows will be given the opportunity:

- To develop their research leadership skills through a dedicated training programme;
- To take part in interdisciplinary scholarly exchange and research networking activities, among Fellows and with the broader EUTOPIA research community;
- To initiate research collaborations within the EUTOPIA Alliance
- To contribute to the development of a challenge-based and student-shaped curriculum, through the development of research-led learning units open to undergraduate and graduate students;
- To act as EUTOPIA ambassadors, contributing to the Alliance's activities and fostering the emergence of an integrated research community at the EUTOPIA scale.

Young Leaders Academy is open to **early to mid-career researchers**, preferably between **2 to 12 years after PhD completion**. YLA Fellows will be appointed for a period of **2 years**.

Applicants should already be formally appointed with one of the Universities of the EUTOPIA Alliance and hold a tenured or tenure-track position or major research fellowship.

Opening date for applications: 30 April 2021
Closing date for applications: 30 June 2021

For full information on the call and the application and selection criteria, please consult the documents below:

[CALL DESCRIPTION \(link\)](#)
[APPLICATION FORM \(link\)](#)

What's new

EUTOPIA University Retweeted

The Guild @TheGuild

The Guild member universities emphasize that collaboration within the #EUTOPIA research initiative needs to grow bottom-up, based on the #alliance's distinctive strategies.

See our recommendations [@EUTOPIA](#)

Retweeted by The Guild on May 21, 2021

EUTOPIA University Retweeted

VUB @VUB

On 28 May, we commemorate the official birthday of our university. We do this by highlighting the social commitment of our students and in active students speak out. One of them is @Anouck. She studies Social Sciences at the VUB and fights for a better world. #TheWorldNeedsYou

Retweeted by VUB on May 28, 2021

EUTOPIA Facebook

EUTOPIA European University

Like Page Show

EUTOPIA European University

All the EUTOPIA partners advertise this call internally by specific emailing to the research groups directors and the researcher's community.

4.3. Appendix 3-Reporting material

The following reporting material may change slightly with potential inputs from the fellows, especially after the first visits.

4.3.1. Researcher mobility programme reporting material

Visit logs

Researcher Name	
Researcher Surname	
Researcher email	
Gender (F/M/Non binary)	
Home university	
Home research group	
Home research lab	
Researcher personal webpage (link)	
Host university	
Host research group	
Host research lab	
Host inviting professor name	
Host inviting professor surname	
Host inviting professor email	
Host inviting professor gender (F/M/NB)	
Host inviting professor personal webpage (link)	
Visit starting date	
Visit end date	
Did you face any problem during your mobility?	
Did you succeeded in carrying out all the planned activities (YES/NO)	
Please acknowledge that you will have to send a visit report, co sent with the host researcher, within 1 month after the end of the visit.	
Date of Visit logs delivery	
Date of Visit Report delivery	

Visit report

Report logs	Researcher Name	
Report logs	Researcher Surname	
Report logs	Researcher email	
Report logs	Gender (F/M/Non binary)	
Report logs	Home university	
Report logs	Home research group	
Report logs	Home research lab	
Report logs	Researcher personal webpage (link)	
Report logs	Host university	
Report logs	Host research group	
Report logs	Host research lab	
Report logs	Host inviting professor name	
Report logs	Host inviting professor surname	
Report logs	Host inviting professor email	
Report logs	Host inviting professor gender (F/M/NB)	
Report logs	Host inviting professor personal webpage (link)	
Report logs	Visit starting date	
Report logs	Visit end date	
Report logs	Did you face any problem during your mobility?	
Report logs	Did you succeeded in carrying out all the planned activities (YES/NO)	
Report logs	Other remarks on your visit	
Report logs	Please acknowledge that you will have to send a visit report, co sent with the host researcher, within 1 month after the end of the visit.	
Report logs	Date of Visit logs delivery	
Report logs	Date of Visit Report delivery	
	Research project title	
	Discipline(s) concerned by the project (please use the nomenclature détailed in the next folder)	
	Key words	
	Description of the activities carried out during the visit (research activities already ongoing, start of new research activities, seminar organization, lectures, innovation or transfer activities , etc.)	
	Indicate the next steps of your collaboration	
	Common publications (ref)	
	Common oral presentation (ref)	
	Common poster presentation (ref)	
	Citizen science common activities (ref)	
	Common training offer (short presentation, ref or links)	
	Common communication activities (short presentation , ref or links)	
	New common research group (if creation of a new reserach group at Eutopia level)	
	Any other remarks (issues, suggestions, ...)	

4.3.2.YLA programme reporting material

Visit report

YL Name	
YL Surname	
YL email	
Gender (F/M/Non binary)	
Home university	
Home research group	
Home research lab	
Discipline (please use the Discipline Nomenclature folder)	
Research topics	
YL personal webpage	
Trainings the fellows attend to during the appointment period (titles of the local or common EUTOPIA trainings)	
Dates & location (or remote)	
Training and lectures the fellow gave during the appointment period (title)	
Date	
Location (Univ or remote)	
Weblink (if applicable)	
Precise if it has been co developed with another fellow, who has to be identified	
Level of the public	
This part concerns the mobilities as Carte blanche within EUTOPIA. Please answer when applicable and use the the section "Other remarks" if necessary. For multiple visits please use additional lines	
Host university	
Host research group	
Host research lab	
Host inviting professor name	
Host inviting professor surname	
Host inviting professor email	
Host inviting professor gender (F/M/NB)	
Host inviting professor personal webpage	
Discipline(s) concerned by the visit/common project	
Project title	
Abstract of the visit outcomes (common project application , common publications, PhD co-supervision, other..)	
Visit start date	
Visit end date	
Description of the activities carried out during the visit	
Indicate the next steps of your collaboration	
Common publications	
Common oral presentation	
common poster presentation	
Citizen science common activities	
Common training offer	
Common communication activities	
Other remarks	